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ASSESSMENT OF THE AWARENESS AND KNOWLEDGE GAP OF CURRICULUM REMODELING OF EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

On the continent of Africa, the two most important developmental agenda are the United Nations Agenda 2030 and the Africa Union Agenda 2063 as all member states have subscribed to these developmental programmes to guide their developmental programmes. In spite of several frameworks put in place for its implementation, studies have shown that implementation frameworks without deliberate educational intervention and curricular restructuring will amount to nothing if concise efforts are not geared towards curricular re-orientation in the educational systems to mobilise support for the implementation of these agenda. Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has proved effective in mobilising support for the implementation of the UN Agenda 2030 but reports shows that it has not been fully explored in Africa especially among Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) many of who are signatories to several conventions and declarations that promotes ESD. Therefore, this study determined the need for a curriculum re-modelling in Higher Education Institutions in Nigeria for effective teaching, learning and practices for Sustainable Development as a framework for achieving the United Nations Agenda 2030 and Africa Union Agenda 2063. The study adopted descriptivemethod of data collection and multistage sampling procedure. The study population consists undergraduatefrom public and private universities in Southwest Nigeria. A total of 2,250 undergraduates were randomly selected from 9 Federal, State and Private Universities. One instrument with three subsections containing A: Demographic information of respondents (5 items), B: Students Awareness of Sustainable Development (15 items) and C; Students Knowledge of Sustainable Development (10 Items) was used to collect data after it had been validated and it yielded the reliability co-efficient of .95 and .91 for sections B and C respectively. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentage scores, mean and standard deviation. Findings showed that there is an awareness and knowledge gap of sustainable development, the SDGs and CESA goals among undergraduates. It was recommended that universities should pursue an urgent curriculum remodeling for teaching and learning of sustainability in Nigeria.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, Curriculum remodeling, Awareness and Knowledge Gap, Nigerian Universities

Introduction

Achieving development goals like the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the African Agenda 2063 require careful planning and strategic implementation frameworks. Through partnerships and collaboration, national governments, multi-national agencies and civil society organisations are expected to device semodels and frameworks to embark on the comprehensive implementation of these programmes. Governments are expected to show strong public commitment to implementing the SDGs and be accountable to the citizens through national formal and informal mechanisms. The civil society groups are expected to play the key role of ensuring

that government strategies target all segments of society and ensure accountability for SDG implementation. (UN SDG Implementation Framework, 2015)

In spite of these frameworks, scholars, and specialized agencies like the United Nations Education and Scientific Organisation (UNESCO) have argued that the intricatenature of these development strategies requires deliberate and carefully crafted education with which the goals could be achieved (Babalola, 2019). For instance, UNESCO maintained that education is the most potent tool to achieve sustainability. Though required, economic policies, technological inventions, political directives or fiscal incentives are not all there is to achieve laudable development goals like the UN Agenda 2030 and Africa's Agenda 2063 (UNESCO, 2014). The argument is in seeking a new direction of teaching and learning for sustainability. Teaching and learning for sustainability have been popularly referred to as Education for Sustainable Development (UNESCO, 2014; Filho, 2015; Babalola, 2019).

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) in its widest sense is education for social reconstruction with a focus of inventing new sustainable communities. Education for Sustainable Development affects all facets of human life and activities including; education, policy development, programme planning and execution, curriculum development, teaching and learning, assessment and administration. Education for Sustainable Development aims to offer an articulate interaction between education, unrestricted public consciousness, and training with the focus of re-inventing an excellent sustainable future for all. (UNESCO 2012; Hofman 2015; and Babalola 2019)

The period of 2005 – 2014 was dedicated by UNESCO as a decade for promoting the principles of Education for Sustainable development in all parts of the world (UNESCO, 2014). The focus of the decade was to transform education systems so they can better equip learners with the skills and knowledge required to respond to the challenges of sustainable development and to contribute to the achievement of SDGs at all levels of education. Through several declarations such as: the Talloires Declaration in 1990, Agenda 21 in 1992, the Kyoto Declaration in 1993, Global Higher Education for Sustainability Partnership in 2000, the Luneburg Declaration in 2001, the Sapporo Declaration in 2002, Graz Declaration in 2005, Abuja Declaration on Sustainable Development in Africa in 2009, the Rio+20 Higher Education Sustainability Initiative, as well as the UN Decade for Education for Sustainable Development, higher education institutions (HEIs) have been assigned a crucial role in making positive input into the execution of sustainable development through education for sustainable development. This is because university staff produces huge numbers of graduates every year in all specialties and are in a convenient position to foster a broader knowledge of what sustainable development entails. (Babalola, 2019).

One of the unique ways through which higher education institutions (HEIs) can significantly contribute to the attainment of these goals is through the instruction of sustainable development concepts by means of curriculum remodeling (Leal 2016; Babalola, 2019). Curriculum remodeling is a process of re-constructing the educational process especially the content of an academic programme to facilitate the advancement and provision of a new direction for the educational system with the goal of keeping abreast with international best practices and global realities. According to Kolawole (2015), Babalola and Kolawole (2021) Curriculum remodeling is an innovative approach of repackaging learning programmes which could involve the design of an entirely new curriculum or a modification of an existing academic programme. In an effort to keep abreast with global changes in the areas of sustainable development and in response to

several international declarations on the need for universities to promote sustainable development through integrated curriculum approach some universities in North America, Europe and Asia have institutionalized sustainable development education into their the curricula and university operations through teaching, research and sustainable campus practices as a means to achieving sustainable development goals by 2030 (Wals, 2014; Beynaghi, Trencher, Moztarzadeh, Mozafari, and Leal, 2016; Babalola, 2019).

Omisore et al. (2017) in a study carried out among university students have decried the low level of undergraduates' awareness and knowledge of sustainable development in Nigerian Universities. In the same vein, Babalola (2019) found a low awareness and knowledge among undergraduates in southwest Nigeriawhile Wojuola and Alant (2019)also found a low awarenessand knowledge of renewable energy technologies among participants in Ibadan metropolis. Moreover, Ogunyemi et al. (2022) found a poor awareness and low knowledge of sustainable development concepts among preservice teachers in Nigeria. The findings of past studies show a consistent low awareness and knowledge of sustainable development among undergraduates calls for a sustainable institutional approach in fixing this problem, hence the need for universities to integrate sustainability into their curricula.

Statement of Problem

A careful review of existing literature on African universities' involvement and practices in integratingsustainabilityinto their curricular and campus operation shows that there a lot to be done in this area. Many universities have not fully integrated the principle of teaching and learning for sustainability in their curricular (Ralph and Stubbs, 2014; Babalola, 2019; Ogunyemi *et al*, 2022) thereby widening knowledge gap with respect to sustainability and impeding its implementation and realisation. UNESCO reports indicated that the concept of sustainable development remains largely an emerging interest among higher education institutions (HEIs) in Africa, especially in Sub-Saharan Africa (UNESCO, 2014). This, however, has created a gap on the robust understanding of what sustainable development entail in all its forms among university graduates from Nigerian universities as many do not possess the basic knowledge of sustainability, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and its direct implications on their social, economic and environmental growth. Therefore, this study determined the need for a curriculum re-modelling in Higher Education Institutions in Nigeria for effective teaching, learning and practices for Sustainable Development as a framework for achieving the United Nations Agenda 2030 and Africa Union Agenda 2063.

Research Questions

1. Would undergraduates' level of awareness of sustainable development principles substantiate the need for curriculum remodeling for Education for Sustainable Development in Nigerian universities?
2. Would undergraduates' level of knowledge of Sustainable Development Goals and CESA authenticate the need for curriculum in Education for Sustainable Development in Nigerian universities?

Methodology

A descriptive survey design of data collection was used in the study. The population for the study are undergraduates in public (federal and state) and private universities in Southwestern part of Nigeria. Purposive random sampling was used to select 9 conventional universities while simple random was used to select 2,250 undergraduates from the 9 universities. A self-constructed

instrument named "Curriculum on Education for Sustainable Development Need Assessment Questionnaire" (CESDNAQ) was used in the study. The instrument was sub-divided into three: Section A Demography containing 5 items, Section B Students Awareness of Sustainable Development containing 15 items on 4 Likert scale of Very Much Aware, Aware, Less Aware and Not Aware. Section C – Students' Knowledge of SD contains 10 open ended question Items on SD. The items in the instruments were validated by experts and the reliability was determined using Cronbach Alpha reliability analysis which yielded reliability co-efficient for section B=0.95, and section C=0.91. Data collection lasted for 9 weeks as one week each was used to collect data in each of the selected institution. Of the 2,250 administered instrument 1,848(82%) were retrieved. Data collected were analysed using frequency count, percentage score, mean and standard deviation. The decision rule was placed at 2.50 since a 4 Likert Scale was used.

Results

Research Question 1: Would undergraduates' level of awareness of sustainable development principles substantiate the need for curriculum remodeling for Education for Sustainable Development in Nigerian universities?

To answer this question, frequency counts and percentage score was used and the results presented in Table 1

Table 1: Summary of the Descriptive Analysis of Nigerian University Undergraduates' Level of Awareness of Sustainable Development

S/N	ITEM	Very Much Aware F (%)	Aware F (%)	Less Aware F (%)	Not Aware F (%)	Mean	STD.
1	Are you aware of: Sustainable Development (SD)?	237 (12.8)	348 (18.8)	326 (17.6)	937 (50.7)	1.94	1.098
2	Are you aware of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?	202 (10.9)	326 (17.7)	384 (20.8)	934 (50.6)	1.89	1.053
3	Education for Sustainable Development (ESD)?	172 (9.5)	309 (17.0)	393 (21.7)	941 (51.8)	1.84	1.021
4	How will you rate your knowledge of Sustainable Development?	163 (8.9)	335 (18.3)	573 (31.3)	761 (41.5)	1.96	1.072
5	Are you aware sustainable development has three focal point?	101 (5.5)	240 (13.1)	453 (24.8)	1031 (56.4)	1.70	1.182
6	Are you aware of your university's strategy on how to achieve Sustainable Development?	149 (8.1)	284 (15.5)	499 (27.2)	901 (49.2)	1.83	.970
7	Are you aware if your university has any centre for research in education and policy development on Sustainable Development?	139 (7.6)	316 (17.2)	481 (26.2)	898 (49.0)	1.83	.969
8	Are you aware if any initiative is being taken by your university to create Sustainable Development awareness in your university?	132 (7.2)	299 (16.3)	482 (26.2)	924 (50.3)	1.80	.957

9	Are you aware of any programme undertaken by your university to educate students towards sustainable development?	197 (10.7)	327 (17.8)	476 (26.0)	834 (45.5)	1.94	1.029
10	Are you aware of any student group directly promoting initiative on sustainable development in your university?	191 (10.5)	327 (17.9)	453 (24.8)	856 (46.9)	1.92	1.029
11	Are you aware of any workshop, seminar, symposium (a conference organised in your university to create awareness on sustainable development for students in recent past?	196 (10.7)	370 (20.2)	449 (24.5)	819 (44.7)	1.97	1.037
12	Are you aware that university education should provide students with education and training needed to cope with demands of sustainable development?	406 (22.1)	538 (29.3)	389 (21.2)	503 (27.4)	2.46	1.113
13	Are you aware Students' knowledge of Sustainable Development would be significantly enhanced in your institution if attempt is made to communicate it formally through an organised curriculum?	382 (20.8)	639 (34.7)	376 (20.4)	438 (23.8)	2.53	1.102
14	Are you aware that offering a course on Sustainable Development can enhance your understanding of the concept of sustainable development?	464 (25.4)	640 (35.0)	332 (18.2)	392 (21.4)	2.64	1.080
15	Are you aware that attending a workshop, seminar, or symposium (a conference on sustainable development can enhance your knowledge of sustainable development	526 (28.7)	667 (36.3)	282 (15.4)	360 (19.6)	2.74	1.076

Weighted Mean = 2.07

Table 1 showed that 1263 representing 68.4% of the students do have any form of awareness about sustainable development. Furthermore, 1,318 representing 71.4% of the students are not aware of Sustainable Development Goals. In the same vein, 1,334 representing 73.5% of the students are not aware of Education for Sustainable Development. Moreover, 1,334 representing 72.8% of the students have a poor knowledge of sustainable development. Over, 80% of the students are not aware that sustainable development has three focal areas.

On attempts taken by universities that could create awareness, more than 1,400 representing 76.4% of the students are not aware of their university's strategy/approach on how to achieve Sustainable Development while 1,379 representing 75.2% of the students are not aware if their universities have any centre for research in education and policy development on Sustainable Development. Moreover, 1,406 (76.5%) of the students are not aware if any initiative is being taken by their universities to create sustainable development awareness. About 1,310, which is more than 70% of the students, are not aware of programmes undertaken by their universities to educate students towards sustainable development. Awareness of student groups directly

promoting initiative on sustainable development on campus is low at over 71% and awareness of any forms of workshops, seminars, symposium or a conference organized by the university to create awareness on sustainable development for students in recent is equally low at 69.2%.

About 51.4% of the students are aware that university education should provide students with education and training needed to cope with demands of sustainable development and 55.5% of the students are aware that Students' knowledge of Sustainable Development would be significantly enhanced in their institution if attempt is made to communicate it formally through an organised curriculum. More than half of the students (60.4%) are aware that offering a course on Sustainable Development can enhance their understanding of the concept of sustainable development while 65.0% of the students are aware that attending a workshop, seminar, symposium or a conference on sustainable development can enhance their knowledge of sustainable development. The weighted mean is less than 2.5 established as the criterion norm. With this trend of finding, the low awareness of undergraduates about sustainable development presents the need to remodel higher education institution curriculum to educate undergraduates for sustainable development.

Research Question 2: Would undergraduates' level of knowledge of Sustainable Development Goals and CESA authenticate the need for a curriculum in Education for Sustainable Development in Nigerian universities?

To answer this question, the table presents the Mean score (average score) of all participants on a score range of 0-35. The SD knowledge score obtained by participants ranged from 0 – 35 (minimum score = 0 and maximum score = 35) The mean score is Presented in Table 2.

Table 2: **Summary of the Descriptive Analysis of University Undergraduates' Level of Knowledge of Sustainable Development Goals**

	Number of participants	Minimum Score	Maximum Score	Mean Score obtained	Std. Deviation
D	1852	0	35	.92	3.721
Valid N (listwise)	1852				

Table 2 presents the undergraduates' level of knowledge of sustainable development. It shows that 0 is the minimum score, while 35 is the maximum score. The total mean score (.92) which is less than 1 shows that the average score of undergraduates' knowledge of the Sustainable Development and the CESA goals is critically low at less than 1. The standard deviation (3.721) is also very scattered. Hence, the low level of undergraduates' knowledge of SD, SDGs and CESA goals as shown by the mean score presents the need for curriculum remodeling for sustainable teaching and learning in higher education institutions in Nigeria.

Discussions

Undergraduates' Level of Awareness of Sustainable Development Principles

Several reasons could be attributed to the very low rate of awareness about sustainable development and the Sustainable Development Goals among undergraduates in Nigerian Universities. As observed by UNESCO, (2014) education for sustainable development is still an emerging concept among Higher Education Institutions in Africa due to the absence of an institutional implementation framework for achieving the goals. Matthias and Rieckmann (2016)

explained that when universities commit to teaching and learning for sustainable development, they will be in the position to form a link between knowledge generation and transfer by educating future decision-makers.

They will also be able to engage in scientific research and new knowledge development for education for sustainable development. Bangar Chhokar (2010), explained that institutions in India to implement sustainability have introduced sustainable development components into their existing programmes, developed specialized programmes around sustainability, designed courses or modules on sustainable development, and greened their campuses amongst others. The reason there appears to be an awareness deficit about sustainable development among undergraduates in Nigeria is largely because universities have not taken proactive steps as could be seen in what has been done in India an example of a developing country.

The low level of awareness of sustainable development and the SDGs justifies the need for the remodeling of higher education institution curriculum to accommodate teaching and learning for sustainability in Nigeria. Ralph and Stubbs (2013) submitted that one of the ways through which universities can demonstrate commitment to sustainability is through fulfilling their moral responsibility of educating future leaders and to advance knowledge that can foster the realisation of sustainability in their environment.

Undergraduates' Level of Knowledge of Sustainable Development and Continental Education Strategy Goals

The findings from the study about basic knowledge of the meaning of sustainable development, the Sustainable Development Goals and the CESA goals presented a very poor level of undergraduates' knowledge of the concepts. Over 92.4% of the undergraduates had zero or no knowledge at all of the concepts and only about 0.8% had adequate knowledge while the rest (6.4%) had an incoherent knowledge of the concepts. This result clearly showed that some of the undergraduates (30%) who earlier claimed to have had awareness about the Sustainable Development Goals in section B of the questionnaire do not have any knowledge about the concept of sustainable development, the SDGs and CESA goals.

This result is a poor reflection of Nigerian universities' commitment to sustainable development which has become a parameter for rating the quality of any university globally. In a study carried out by Emmanuel and Adams in (2011) in Alabama and Hawaii to find out undergraduates' knowledge of sustainable development, they found out that a larger proportion of the student of the Alabama and the Hawaii students had a significant knowledge of sustainable development especially when asked to identify the term they do associate with sustainability. Furthermore, in a study named the Sustainable Literacy Test conducted by the Higher Education Sustainability Initiative's (HESI) in 2017 among 170 universities by (Mula, et al, 2017) it was reported that undergraduates had relatively high homogenous awareness of the SDGs even though none of them had complete awareness of the SDGs. This is not in agreement with the finding of this study, and it can be attributed to a lot of reasons. The first being that many universities in the developed nations have utilised the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development to scale up activities to integrate education for sustainable development into their curricula, campus operation and university administration and as rightly described by UNESCO (2014), several of the indicators of advancement in teaching and learning (education) for Sustainable Development in tertiary institutions emanates from Latin America and Europe.

It is against this backdrop that the findings of HESI 2017 cannot be applied to Nigerian Context where teaching and learning for sustainability has not been given its prime place. In a similar study carried out by Omisore et al. (2017), among university lecturers and students in a university in Southwest Nigeria, they found a low level of awareness of students and lecturers about the sustainable development goals and decried the low level as a result of non-teaching and learning about the SDGs and little or no research about sustainable development related issues. Low level of sustainable development awareness in a university community is detrimental to the future of the SDGs and CESA goals in Nigeria especially since universities have been assigned a leading role in many important pronouncements such as the Talloires Declaration of 1990, Agenda 21 in 1992, the Kyoto Declaration of 1993, the Global Higher Education for Sustainability Partnerships in 2000 (Babalola, 2016). If the SDGs would be achieved in Nigeria by 2030 universities have to wake up to their role in promoting sustainable development through a viable curriculum remodeling for the teaching and learning for sustainable development.

Conclusion

The 2030 agenda of the United Nations and the 2063 Agenda have placed a huge responsibility on universities to redesign their curricular to accommodate the teaching and learning for sustainability. This study surveyed the observed gap in Nigerian university undergraduates' awareness and knowledge of United Nations sustainable agenda, and African Union CESA goals. The study found that there is a wide gap in undergraduates students' awareness of sustainable development concepts, the SDGs and the CESA goals.

The study also found that the knowledge of Undergraduates about sustainable development and the UN and AU development agenda known as the SDGs and CESA is poor and cannot be compared with similar studies in other parts of the world. While it was observed that this result could not have been different due to the lack of teaching and learning for sustainability in Nigerian universities and active sustainable implementation frameworks in these institutions, it was recommended that higher education institutions in Nigeria in fulfilling their moral responsibility of educating, implementing and mobilizing supports for the realisation of development agenda such as considered in this study, should as a matter of urgency pursue a curriculum remodeling effort to keep abreast with implementing these all important development agenda.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the recommendations:

1. Universities in Nigeria should pursue urgent and aggressive curriculum remodeling plan to integrate teaching and learning for sustainable development in their curricula. This can be done using multi-level approaches.
2. Higher education institutions should design a sustainable implementation framework that is available to students and staff in the university, through which their short, medium and long-term goals for sustainability can be communicated.
3. Regular outreaches, seminars and workshops should be done on sustainable development on campus and even in surrounding communities.
4. Specialised academic programmes, courses or short courses in cohorts for sustainable development should be created.
5. Students clubs, associations, hubs and spaces that will promote students campus involvement in sustainable development should be created.

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